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Applications of cosmic-ray muon imaging in Earth Sciences

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Introduction

Primary high-energy cosmic radiation bombards Earth's atmosphere everywhere and at all times, generating a constantly present source of highly-penetrating elementary particles called muons. Once the almost light-speed fast muons reach the ground, they start losing energy faster than they do in the relatively thin air. The unique properties of muons allow density imaging of materials in a new way: muographically. (Cosmic-ray) muography – or muon imaging – is a novel particle geophysical method that works analogously to X-ray imaging in that muon radiation, like X-rays, is attenuated as a function of the material density. In Earth Sciences, muon imaging is conducted chiefly as muon attenuation radiography that provides 2D density images. If the same volume is observed from multiple directions, the produced density models can obtain a 3rd dimension. This technique is muon attenuation tomography. In addition, lengthy radiography or tomography measurements can be used for monitoring density changes over time.

Muon imaging in Earth Sciences

Applications include volcanoes (Oláh & Tanaka, 2022; Leone et al., 2021), aquifers (Lázaro Roche et al., 2022), rock strata and structural geological problems (Holma et al., 2022b), ore deposits (Holma et al., 2022c), mining and tunnelling operations (Zhang et al., 2021), glacier-bedrock interfaces (Scampoli et al., 2022), and karst mapping (Hamar et al., 2022). A few studies have focused on the oceans (Tanaka et al., 2021, 2022a) and even the atmosphere (Tanaka et al., 2022b). Applications employed on the Moon, Mars and asteroids have also been proposed.

The talk aims to bring muography and its many Earth Science applications better known in Finland. Proposed Earth Sciences applications in Finland include groundwater, mineral exploration and mining, Quaternary geology, weathering studies, impact craters, geothermal research, environmental studies and soil and rock characterisation. A recently commenced series in the Finnish magazine “Geologi” represents the principles, background story and applications of muography in detail for the first time in the Finnish language (Holma et al., 2022a). Finnish geoscientists are encouraged to consider muography as an additional tool in their respective research fields.

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The 1st GeoDays of Finland is held at the Kumpula campus of the University of Helsinki, 14th–17th March 2023. The event gathers over 100 experts from different fields of geosciences to present and learn from the latest research and innovations. This publication contains the program and submitted abstracts for all the oral and poster presentations held at the event. The organizing committee would like to express gratitude to all the authors for their contributions.

Visit www.geologinenseura.fi for information regarding the next GeoDays!

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